

INTRODUCE THE NEGATIVE INFLUENCE IN VIETNAM IF JAPAN DISCHARGES THE NUCLEAR SEWAGE TO PACIFIC

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1. Synopsis

Since the Fukushima Daiichi nuclear accident, which was precipitated by the 2011 Thoku earthquake and tsunami on March 11, 2011, radioactive waste water has been dumped into the Pacific Ocean. The majority of the radioactive materials were released into the sky immediately following the incident, with 80 percent eventually settling over the Pacific (and some over rivers). Since then, there has been groundwater leakage, which the nuclear facility officially confirmed to in 2013. Water treatment began in 2013 as "Advanced Liquid Processing System" become operable, which remove most radionuclides except tritium. In 2021, the Japanese cabinet approved the dumping of the water into the Pacific over a course of 30 years.

Japan recently announced plans to discharge over 1.2 million tons of radioactive water from the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant (FDNPP) into the Pacific Ocean. The contaminated water can poses a threat to marine ecosystems and human health. To assess the plan's impact, we created a three-dimensional global model to follow the movement and dispersion of tritium emitted from the FDNPP's radioactive water. The pollution scenarios were simulated for four release durations (1 month, 1 year, 5 years, and 10 years). According to the modeling results, for short-duration scenarios (1 month and 1 year), the peak plume with high tritium content drifted with the currents and eventually reached the northeastern Pacific. The greatest plume of contaminated water was confined to coastal locations east of Japan in the long-duration scenarios (5 and 10 years).

Since 2013, there has been tritium groundwater leakage to the land side of the Fukushima Dai-ichi nuclear power reactors. From the end of 2013 until the end of 2019, groundwater was continuously collected, with an average tritium content of about 20 Bq/L. Based on tritium data supplied by Tokyo Electric Power Company Holdings (TEPCO) (17,000 points), the cause of the leak was either I leaks from a polluted water tank that happened between 2013 and 2014, or (ii) a tritium leak that had spread widely over an impervious layer under the site. Vietnam also intends to build nuclear power stations, with 13 reactors set to be completed by 2030. As a result, by 2035, the number of nuclear power facilities in Asia is predicted to nearly triple. As a result, if the aforementioned occurrence occurs, it can be used as a reference lesson.

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2. Economic situation with coastal provinces of Vietnam

So, in October 2011, the center organized a nuclear security conference in Vietnam, and in March 2012, they organized a session at the Integrated Support Center for 10 operators from Vietnam Electricity on peaceful uses of nuclear energy and nuclear nonproliferation/security. In addition, in July 2012, the center sponsored a workshop in Da Lat, Vietnam, on the subject of declarations based on the IAEA Additional Protocol, in collaboration with the IAEA, the United States, the Nuclear Material Control Center, and others.

Environmental emission crisis Formosa 2016 admits that they have discharged about 12 thousand m³ of wastewater into the sea every day in the past time and affirmed that all wastewater samples tested by them are up to standards. According to another estimate, with the scale of the waste pipeline buried 1.5 km under the seabed, it is capable of discharging to the environment a maximum of 300 thousand m³ of wastewater per day. If it contains toxic substances, then depending on the type, it can easily cause disaster to destroy a large sea area if the toxicity is high. Taking place according to a definite route starting from Vung Ang - Ha Tinh, fish began to die gradually spreading to the coastal areas of Quang Binh, Quang Tri and then Hue, in line with the ocean currents according to the map of the Institute of Science. study irrigation. In winter, the coastal current of Vietnam flows in the North-South direction, that is, if from Ha Tinh, it will flow into

Quang Binh, Quang Tri and then Hue. The time when the fish started to die was early April 2016, spreading according to the current. Around August, summer, the current will change direction and flow from South to North. Obviously, a province adjacent to Ha Tinh is Nghe An, but in the north against the current, there are no dead fish.

Up to now, aquaculture production and people's lives in 28 coastal provinces have basically stabilized from 2017-2021. Aquatic resources have recovered, many types of fish, shellfish... reappeared. People actively stick to the sea, step by step converting bottom-floor mining to offshore fishing. The number of boats exploiting inshore reaches the rate of 70-80%; vessels exploiting the inland and offshore areas reach 85-90%. Mining output seafood quarter raising 1/2018 reached 25386 tons down 8.8% compared to the same period in 2017 (Ha Tinh: 5689 tons, down 22.6%, Quang Binh: 8975 tons, down 1.8%; Quang Tri: 4,300 tons, up 3.6%; Thua Thien Hue: 6,422 tons, down 14.7%). Aquaculture output equivalent to the same period in 2017. The total output of the 04 provinces in the quarter raising 1/2018 is 6279 tons, an increase of 3.12% over the same period in 2016 (Ha Tinh: 2,475 tons fell 8.8%, Quang Binh: 1,447 tons, down 4%; Quang Tri: 1,480 tons, up 19%; Thua Thien Hue: 877 tons, up 6.3%).

Regarding seafood business: The business of trading and retailing seafood has resumed operations. Consumers have consumed marine seafood products, especially freshly

caught seafood products. Localities are actively consuming stored seafood to ensure food safety. However, the operation of seafood enterprises, production and processing establishments still has some difficulties in terms of facilities, lack of capital in the production process, and consumers' concerns...

Regarding salt production: Currently, it is not yet the season for salt production, but localities and salt farmers are actively preparing for salt production in the summer of 2021.

Regarding tourism: The provinces have focused on promoting cooperation, association, tourism promotion, improvement and upgrading of accommodation facilities. However, due to lack of the tourist season, especially due to translation Covid-19 should quarter 2021, the number of tourists is not much the central provinces.

We created and enhanced Safety Standards, norms, and guidelines. The Vienna Declaration brought all parties to the Convention on Nuclear Safety together to support its principles. The Fukushima disaster taught us that regulators must be powerful, independent, and well-funded.

3. Overall assessment if the same happens

Take a typical example of an incident that happened in Vietnam (Formosa crisis in Vung Ang, Ha Tinh 2016). On June 6, 2016, fisherman Nguyen Xuan Thanh, Ky Anh town, Ha Tinh province found a giant pipe about 1.5 km long, about 1.1 meters in diameter, running from Formosa Vung Ang to the sea. Place on the surface of the seabed and

cover with sandbags and rocks. The liquid pumped very strongly from the inside of the tube into the seabed is opaque yellow, viscous, with a strong odor. On November 4, 2016, the Vietnam National Administration of Tourism announced the operation of the first 10 months of the year, showing that Quang Binh was the most damaged province with a loss exceeding 1,500 billion VND. Nghe An, Quang Tri, Ha Tinh and Thua Thien Hue also suffered tourism damage. The national tourism agency said waste pollution from the Formosa company along the central coast in April had almost completely destroyed the region's tourism industry as revenue from tourism dropped by as much as 90%.

With the environmental disaster occurring in the coastal areas of Vietnam, the province will lose tens of billions of dollars a year in the short term due to loss of tourism revenue, not to mention transport fishing and aquaculture, which is about a few dozen times higher than that of Vietnam. the amount obtained. Vietnam is also maintaining its planned introduction of nuclear power, while placing highest priority on safety

4. Issues that need further discussion

The main features or attributes of the accidents that occurred at Chernobyl Nuclear Power Station (CNPS) and Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Station (FDNPS) from peer-reviewed scientific reports in the discuss below together with estimates of the resulting exposures of, and health effects in, coastal workers and fishermen. The consequences of the

accident at FDNPS were much lower than those at CNPS (e.g., for the FDNPS accident, estimated average effective doses to adult evacuees were less than about 6 mSv and average absorbed doses to the thyroid were less than about 15 mGy, compared with around 30 mSv and 500 mGy for the CNPS accident). Not to mention the discharge into sea water is strictly controlled and with the allowable concentration under the influence of ocean currents and sea salt with great intensity, the ability to mix and spread will have very low or no impact.

- (a) A much larger fraction of the more significant radionuclides (isotopes of iodine and caesium) in the fuel of the respective reactors (also referred as units) was released to the environment from CNPS than FDNPS. The reactors at FDNPS had purpose-built containments within which most of the radionuclides released from the molten fuel were retained; by contrast, the reactor at CNPS did not have a containment and the core was directly exposed to the atmosphere as a result of the explosion that occurred at the beginning of the accident;
- (b) The explosion at CNPS resulted in a fire on the roof of the reactor and turbine buildings that had to be extinguished to minimize the risk of the accident escalating and propagating to other reactor units. In this process more than a hundred emergency workers were exposed to high levels of radiation (exposure of the whole body to external radiation and of the skin to beta radiation) that resulted in acute radiation syndrome (ARS);
- (c) The radionuclides released to the atmosphere from CNPS were dispersed and largely deposited over the land mass of Europe. By contrast, some 80% of the release to the atmosphere from FDNPS was dispersed and largely deposited over the Pacific Ocean, where the consequences (in terms of doses to and effects on humans) were considerably less than for radionuclides dispersed and deposited over land. Beyond the evacuation area, deposition densities were also much lower from Fukushima compared with Chernobyl;
- (d) The accident at FDNPS occurred earlier in the agricultural growing season than that at CNPS (11 March compared with 26 April) with the result that a much lower fraction of deposited radionuclides was transferred to foodstuffs;
- (e) The binding or fixation of radiocaesium in many soils in Japan and in the former Soviet Union is broadly comparable, as is its bioavailability. However, much enhanced and sustained uptake of radiocaesium occurred from some poor agricultural soils (sandy, organic) that occurred in affected regions of Belarus, the Russian Federation and Ukraine around CNPS and in highly organic and upland soils in Western Europe. There is no evidence of such enhanced uptake from Japanese soils;
- (f) Agricultural practice and animal husbandry differ between Japan and the former Soviet Union (i.e., in Japan by far the majority of cattle are housed in barns and do not graze pasture) with the result that the transfer of radionuclides to milk and meat following the accident at FDNPS was much lower;
- (g) Protective measures (in respect of people, e.g., precautionary evacuation,

and foodstuffs) were implemented more effectively following the accident at FDNPS than at CNPS, resulting in a larger fraction of the potential doses being averted;

- (h) The failure to inform the population, in particular in more rural areas, of the need to restrict or avoid the consumption of potentially affected foodstuffs especially milk, following the accident at CNPS resulted in very large doses to the thyroids of many people and an increased incidence, attributable to radiation exposure, of thyroid cancer, in particular among those who were children at the time;
- (i) The restrictions imposed in Japan on the concentrations of radionuclides in foodstuffs that were marketed for consumption were much lower than in the former Soviet Union, resulting in lower doses from ingestion.

Because there is no scientific evidence to conclude that the negative effects will occur if discharge in the marine environment will affect coastal or island countries in Asia Pacific. Therefore, further discussion is needed. Results of monitoring, evaluation and determination of the extent and scope of environmental pollution and degradation of marine ecosystems in Vietnam's waters, mainly in the central provinces. The assessment results show that mainly negative effects occur as follows: sea water quality, most parameters are within the allowable limits, only a few areas are from Quang Ninh to Ca Mau waters. has the value of iron index in the bottom layer, if it exceeds the permissible threshold of QCVN (National Technical Regulation), it will

affect the water environment; the quality of marine sediments was within the specified limits; on evaluating the adhesion film of the iron colloidal system that adsorbs the toxins Phenol, Cyanide,... there will be a yellow film on the seabed, however, this cling film has decreased much over time due to the action of current ocean currents, the phenol content in the colloidal iron film will also decrease sharply; Coral reef, seagrass and marine ecosystems will recover.

All nuclear power reactors in normal operation discharge tritium-containing water that has been diluted to the required standard specifications. Experience has proved that this is quite safe, but most of the public was unaware of it at first. Furthermore, we are discussing very polluted water this time. Following the accident, debris from radioactive fuel leaked into groundwater and mingled with water in a tritium-containing cooling system. As a result, radioactively contaminated water is discharged into the sewer and treated by ALPS. Author believe that during treatment, the water intended to be discharged has been diluted to the required concentration and meets safety standards, so from a scientific point of view there should be no problems.

The most critical aspect of dealing with the tritium discharge is to make it apparent to everyone that this is absolutely necessary in order to continue working on the damaged reactors.

Figure1. Marine Pollution Map from the U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) | Source: Quora

5. Conclude

It is an outrage that the Japanese government and TEPCO believe they can justify the purposeful dumping of nuclear waste into the Pacific Ocean in the twenty-first century, when the globe and, in particular, the world's oceans face so many difficulties and risks. The decision violates Japan's legal duties under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and will be vigorously opposed in the coming months.

The long-term and silent discharge, if not well controlled, will seriously affect coastal countries. The impact is currently unknown because there are no clear and accurate results on the toxicity of environmental radiation. Before the great pollution of the central

sea and the consequences of Formosa 2016, author think it is important to pay attention and be more careful:

i/ Implement all measures to support coastal people in the host country. Temporarily suspend the use of waste pipelines if the economic benefits that environmental impacts bring cannot be assessed. Vietnam is an example.

ii/ Quickly find out dangerous poisons tritium in the sea if they can't be dissolved.

iii/ Having strict control measures, not letting the discharge cause pollution if there is no environmental impact assessment.

iv/ Willing to cancel plans related to discharge, if the potential hazards

caused by the project cannot be eliminated.

Studies demonstrate that it is safe because the ocean is so large that the

chemical is diluted, but this sets a precedent that anyone can dump nuclear waste on Pacific seas.

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